

represents a repeating decimal), as described in Appendix A. Then, the iterative search begins by setting $d_{cur} = 0$ (the lower bound) and tree bucket bounds are computed, and for $d_{cur} = 0$ only the tree of the exact same size is looked up, i.e. T_8 (or the right tree in Figure 6).

The lookup in T_8 begins initializing the acceptance, pending and traversing queues. Since they are empty, we continue by comparing the query vector to the root vector (i.e., template #4). Their distance is 0.2 because they differ exactly in one token (starting vs completed). Since $0.2 > d_{cur}$, we save it in the acceptance queue, meaning that such centroid will only be accepted if d_{cur} ever reaches 0.2 . Next, the distance to the children of centroid #4 are used to decide if they should be traversed. Because $|0.2 - 0.2| \leq d_{cur}$ (i.e., the absolute difference between the distance of the query to root #4 and the distance between the root and child #1), centroid #1 should be traversed to. On the contrary, centroid #3 should not because $|0.2 - 0.5| > 0$ and therefore it gets added to the restart queue with distance 0.32 . This means that the branch with distance 0.5 would not be explored until d_{cur} reaches 0.32 . Since there are no more children, we go through each element of the traverse queue, which in this case corresponds only to #1. The process then repeats. The comparison of #1 to the current query yields a distance of 0, and therefore #1 is accepted. Note that this centroid is the exact same element as the query, and that it actually contains 3 logs from the input. Thus, we need to find only one more log to satisfy $k = 4$.

Since no more children exist, and the traverse queue is empty (we just popped #1), the current search is done, and since the number of retrieved elements is less than requested, we need to perform another search with a larger distance. The new distance is chosen between the minimum of the pending acceptance queue, the restart queue, and the minimum distance required to explore the closest smaller or larger tree (see Equation 3). The minimum of the queues is 0.2 , and the minimum distance needed to explore the next smaller tree (of size 6) is 0.25 . Therefore, the distance from the queues is selected.

The next search starts with $d_{cur} = 0.2$, and this means we still only explore the tree of size 8. Since the pending acceptance and restart queues are not empty, the search begins therefrom. The pending queue head is element #4 (which was the first element we compared to) with distance 0.2 , and since it is equal to d_{cur} , we can finally accept it and add it to the output set. Note that we already have $k = 4$ elements retrieved (three from template #1 and one from template #4), however we cannot early cancel yet because there might be more elements whose distance may lie between the increment of the previous d_{cur} and the new one (i.e., from $d_{prev} = 0$ to $d_{cur} = 0.2$). Therefore, we continue exploring. The head of the restart queue has element #3 with distance 0.32 , which is larger than 0.2 and thus we do not pop it. Similarly, the traverse queue is empty (since no elements from the restart queue were transferred), and there are no further children to explore from the current node. This means we cannot find more elements with distance $\leq d_{cur}$ and therefore we finish the current search. Notice that the tree of size 6 was not explored because the current distance does not allow it, thus pruning the search space. Similarly, we did not have to traverse and compare to node #3 because its distance was too high.

Last, we sort the four elements retrieved, resulting in

```

d = 0.0 → (<TIME> <NUM> INFO data: block <NUM> is starting)
203615 11 INFO data: block 0 is starting
203615 11 INFO data: block 1 is starting
203630 11 INFO data: block 2 is starting

d = 0.2 → (<TIME> <NUM> INFO data: block <NUM> is completed)
203901 11 INFO data: block 2 is completed

```

These are the four closest elements to the initial query.

C RETRIEVAL ACCURACY FOR DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS

Figure 7 shows the extended box plot for the retrieval accuracy scenario. Noteworthy is the inclusion of the E5 model with masked logs (as a result of the regular expression preprocessing) and the fine-tuned HNSW (HNSW* in the plot) with higher parameters, namely $m=320$ and $\text{beamWidth}=1000$ (i.e., ten times the defaults) which shows improved WF1, although at the expense of increased run-time.

Figure 7: Weighted F1 score for an extended set of different configurations of NN search. Each method is described by two keys, namely the source of the vectors and the search algorithm. Each key stands for (from left to right): Weighted Jaccard (WJ), BK-Tree (BK), HNSW (HNSW), fine-tuned E5 embedding model (E5f), cosine similarity (CS) and FastText (FT). The m modifier stands for masked, where the input logs have been preprocessed with regular expressions as it is done in the proposed approach. The * means fine-tuned parameters for the search space.

D ANALYSIS OF THE WORST RETRIEVALS IN THE PROPOSED METHOD

In Section 4.4 and Figure 2, it can be seen that the proposed method has two minimum data points outside the interquartile range in the box plot, one for the LogHub 1.0 dataset and one for the LogHub 2.0. The first one corresponds to the Spark dataset and the second one to the Proxifier dataset. We will analyse why the semantic differences that make up for a lower WF1 are not significant.

Figure 8: Counts of the size of the retrieved clusters in the retrieval accuracy for HNSW where the F1 score is below < 0.5. Counts are only from the LogHub 1.0 dataset. Note that the Apache dataset is not shown because it does not include any F1 scores below 0.1.

D.1 Spark in LogHub 1.0

The Spark dataset achieves a weighted F1 score of 0.8857909. Note that the F1 score is 0.99175446. The difference occurs because several of the annotated templates in LogHub 1.0 are similar enough that the variable part can make up for the same distance depending on its content.

For example, for templates E2 and E3:

```
Block <*> stored as bytes in memory (estimated size <*>, free <*>)
Block <*> stored as values in memory (estimated size <*>, free <*>)
```

As well as the following ones for templates E13 to E17:

```
mapred.job.id is deprecated. Instead, use mapreduce.job.id
mapred.task.id is deprecated. Instead, use mapreduce.task.attempt.id
mapred.task.is.map is deprecated. Instead, use mapreduce.task.ismap
mapred.task.partition is deprecated. Instead, use mapreduce.task.partition
mapred.tip.id is deprecated. Instead, use mapreduce.task.id
```

This is a result of over-masking. For example, the template E13 gets masked into:

```
<URL> is deprecated. Instead, use <URL>
```

Which is then applicable to all five templates. While this behavior may or may not be desirable, the semantic and structural distance between each of the templates is quite low.

D.2 Proxifier in LogHub 2.0

For the Proxifier dataset in LogHub 2.0, the weighted F1 score goes down to 0.83117431. However, in a similar fashion to Spark, the templates responsible for such variations are quite close in terms of both semantic and structural meaning (templates 6 to 9):

```
<*> close, <*> bytes (<*>) sent, <*> bytes (<*>) received, lifetime <*>
<*> close, <*> bytes (<*>) sent, <*> bytes received, lifetime <*>
<*> close, <*> bytes sent, <*> bytes (<*>) received, lifetime <*>
<*> close, <*> bytes sent, <*> bytes received, lifetime <*>
```

Therefore, we argue that the two datasets where the WF1 drops below < 0.9 are only in cases where the retrieved elements are structurally and semantically similar.

E HNSW MISSING ON SMALLER CLUSTERS

Figure 8 depicts a histogram showing the sizes of the clusters for which the retrieved elements have an F1 score below < 0.5 in HNSW. As can be seen, most counts are in the lower range of the histogram, meaning that HNSW has the most trouble when retrieving single-element clusters or small clusters in general. This might happen due to its non-determinism, for instance, if the random search start is not adequate for finding a path to the searched node, or if it gets stuck in a local minimum. Note that if the search parameters are increased to the point where the search becomes exhaustive, HNSW can indeed find all elements.